

Voxel-based analysis of long-term monitored bio-based building elements

Martin Tamke¹[0000-0003-1209-4967], Shahriar Akbari¹[0009-0007-1293-4985]
and Mette Ramsgaard Thomsen¹[0000-0002-3093-8556]

¹ Centre for Information Technology and Architecture (CITA), Royal Danish Academy,
Copenhagen, Denmark.
Martin.Tamke@kgla.kademi.dk

Abstract. This paper introduces an innovative method for tracking and analysing the three-dimensional behaviour of materials outdoors, focusing on bio-based building elements. The constraints of current methods limit monitoring material changes over time to 2D snapshots of an initial and final state. We propose a system utilizing low-cost components like depth cameras and IoT sensors that allow for frequent 3D scans over long periods and overcome challenges such as weather conditions and IR interference. Our method includes a novel automated analysis system, which converts 3D scan data into voxel models for comprehensive evaluation. Our analysis can include different parts of the tracked properties, such as colour, depth and position, which allows us in this way to track changes on overall, region, and feature levels. This approach opens avenues for better understanding material behaviour and its implications for future design, construction and maintenance practices.

Keywords: Long-term monitoring, 3D scan, voxel-based modelling, Material Behaviour.

1 Introduction

The class of bio-based materials becomes more prominent in the building sector due to its transition from a material base in non-renewable sources of the geosphere to renewable resources of the biosphere. Materials, such as biopolymers, are characterised by strong behaviours in response to environmental factors such as humidity, temperature, and rain and have a relatively short life span [1]. These behaviours depend on the material's local sources, recipe, and the objects' geometrical configuration as the environment it is placed in [2]. To develop and establish future practices of design and maintenance it is mandatory to observe and analyse the behaviour of these new materials classes in real-world conditions.

2 Background

Current approaches for long-term observation of structures and materials are either concerned with the effect of weather on new materials or constructions [3], the detection of damages in buildings and infrastructures [4], [5] or the detection of deformation of structures over time [6], [7]. They consist of three steps: **data capturing, processing and analysis** and aim generally at the detection of change. This is mostly achieved by comparing a previous or initial state with the current one. The time interval between the capturing of data is usually quite long - in the case of buildings and infrastructures often years. While the detection of a change is often straight forward, the reason and course of the change's development relies on expert knowledge and is time and capital intensive. The method is as well of limited use in several cases, that are of importance in the development of novel bio-materials: 1) if knowledge does not (yet) exist, 2) changes take place over a short period of time or 3) it is important to understand the exact development of change over time.

Except for remote camera-based time-lapses, current workflows with human, camera or 3D scanning [6], [7] based monitoring are costly in time and/or necessary capital. This contributes to long intervals between inspections, relatively small amount of captured data, which can be processed and analysed with relatively little automation. This is though needed to handle novel computer vision-based approaches towards monitoring. These have shown significant improvements in the detection of changes in building materials. These image-based approaches are however not capable to track spatial movements, as e.g. warpage and shrinkage of materials look the same in the picture plane. 3D scanning [8] solves this problem and some research is undertaken to automate the analysis of 3D data of buildings, e.g. to detect cracks in concrete structures [4]. This paper investigates a new method that automatically 3D scans in short intervals, and processes and analyses the captured spatial data to document and reason about the material behaviour of a novel class of biopolymers.

Fig. 1. Monitoring rig with bio-polymer sample set and the instrument arm, that carries the Depth camera. The right image shows a placement, which is improved in regards to impact of precipitation.

3 Long-term 3D monitoring framework and dataflow

To be widely adopted and open we conduct the outdoor **3D data capturing** with low-cost components: a depth camera (Azure Kinect), IOT sensors, measuring local luminosity, temperature and humidity, and a single board computer (Nvidia Jetson Xavier NX), which serves for automation and as data buffer. This system is embedded into the EMA monitoring framework [9], which is used to dispatch data into the cloud and automate processing and analysis of data.

Outdoor conditions are challenging for monitoring, as weather interferes with electronics, as well as vision-based systems [10]. While custom designed enclosures (Fig.1) and after some testing a rain repellent orientation of all components countered humidity, we found in our experiments precipitation and IR radiation from the sun interfere with IR rays from the 3D scanner [11] disrupting the data collection. To mitigate this, 3D scans are taken in three different lighting conditions: before sunrise and after sunset to avoid direct sunlight and total darkness and at noon, when the amount of light is at its maximum which helps with capturing colours correctly. We find in a coordinate projection analysis of the 3D scans (Fig.2), that the range of Z-axis values of the points in the 3D scans increases often at noon, and conclude, that this is due to the increase in the amount of IR rays. We use therefore only 3D scan data taken at the same time of day for analysis.

Fig. 2. Plot of the range of Z-axis values in 12 days in March 2023, showing that the range increases regularly at noon.

We validated the choice of scanners and the achieved data quality in depth [12] and found that our scans have a deviation of up to 4mm between positions in the scans and physical objects and show a noise level of 0.15mm - 3.10mm between repeated scans. We find that these values are sufficient for our purpose within the range of terrestrial 3D scanners commonly used in the building industry.

Data processing is needed to extract data, specific to the objects, from the initial scans (Fig.5) and to align (register) these. As the Azure Camera is designed to stream depth and color information continuously into a MKV files, we had to adapt this method to take short snapshots of a point in time. Our framework captures in short intervals, transfers the data from the minicomputer into a cloud storage, where the EMA framework allows to automatically process the data into a single averaged dataset using the Microsoft Azure SDK. This dataset is then further processed for analysis, using manual tools, such as CloudCompare or custom scripts, partially integrated in Rhino GH. Details about the evolution and capacities of the different data processing approaches is given in chapter 5.

4 Case: Monitoring biopolymer panels

We evaluate our method by tracking the deformation of 3D Printed Bio-polymer panels over time. The main material components are collagen (bone glue) binder and reinforcing cellulose fibres [2]. After fabrication, the prints undergo a curing stage indoors before they are exposed to outdoor conditions in Copenhagen. We exposed 3D printed samples on our south-west facing monitoring rig. The captured data includes 3D scans, local sensor data, as well as data from a weather station on site. We conducted two **data capture sessions**: the first from 05-08.2023 with a set of eight small bio-polymer panels (Fig. 1), which were held only at the top. Depending on the material composition of the panels, this resulted in partially extreme warping (Fig. 3). The second data capturing session took place from 02-04.2024. We monitored an individual large panel printed from multiple bio-polymer materials. This was held on top and bottom and deformed only moderately.

Fig. 3. Panel 4 at start and end of data capture session (images to the left) The Cloud to Cloud false colour analysis of the 3D point cloud dataset of the panels (Top view on the right) shows the degree of deformation of the panel. For reasons of legibility the scans positions are shifted.

The first experiment was plagued by insufficiencies of our developing framework, due to water intrusion, power and internet losses, so that the whole period only produced 5 usable datasets. These cover however the full period. Our second data capturing campaign was more successful and resulted in daily monitoring over a period of one month without interruption.

During the experiments we conducted experiments to find the best interval of the 3D scans to capture the deformation of the panels and found one per 24hrs to be sufficient. While we experimented as well with weather dependent scheduling we found that a scan at dusk was the most straightforward and best working approach.

5 Analysis of long-term behaviour

The amount and type of data, which automated 3D monitoring produces requires new ways of analysis. During our project, we have developed a set of methods that allow

to analyse an objects' change from a *global – point based* - to a *detailed feature-based* level. Our methods are flexible and combinable, which allows us to extended and hybridise them. Here we can integrate further captured information, as on surface color, allowing us to extract information on the *behaviour of regions* in an object over time.

The methods evolved over the course of our research. Initial manual approaches, get refined, as we start to ask for more specific answers from the datasets. Finally we establish data-pipelines, that can be programmed and are able to perform all analysis methods, that we describe in the following in a highly automated way.

5.1 Global behaviour analysis – point based

To understand the overall behaviour of the 3D printed panels and the type of changes, we extract the point clouds of the panels manually in CloudCompare and use the Cloud to Cloud Distance analysis on the data of the first data capture session. Even though the intervals between scans are several weeks, the comparison of the panels analysis incremental geometric change allows to visually depict whether the degree the panels expanded, warped or protruded. The juxtaposition with weather data reveals the cause for the behaviour of the Biobased materials over time (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4. Analysis of the deformation of a small panel from the first data capture session over time and correlation to weather data. We compare the incremental geometric change of the panel at 5 points in time (12.05.2023, 02.06.2023, 26.06.2023, 17.07.2023, 07.08.2023). The histograms show that the rate of change increases. These changes are initially only small (blue spectrum), while changes are later more evenly distributed over the spectrum.

5.2 Global behaviour analysis - depth information based

Shorter intervals between data captures provide means to follow changes in the objects in more detail. The increased data volume from the second data capture session, necessitate automated data processing. The aim here is to isolate and align the data of the panels from the overall scans. Our initial experiments with a simple Z-value filtering, did not produce sufficient data. Since our panels have thin layers close to the green screen, the resolution of the 3D scans does not allow for an accurate object isolation.

We found as well that some scans are corrupt, and their point clouds show extreme outliers (splatters), probably because of outdoor conditions or processing issues, which need to be filtered out.

Fig. 5. Multistage data process to extract panel data automatically.

We develop therefor a custom multistage data-processing pipeline to isolate the Panels in the overall 3D scans (Fig. 5).

1. 3D scans are pre-processed to be calibrated using Extrinsic (location and orientation of camera), Intrinsic (optical centre and focal length) transformation and Mode specific calibration for Narrow Field of View and are converted from MKV format to Ply format using Azure Kinect SDK. Faulty scans are detected by comparing the range of Z-values to previous and later scans and discarded.
2. The point clouds are aligned with global XYZ directions using the minimum oriented bounding box direction of the point cloud with the centre of point cloud as rotation axis to achieve a coarse alignment.

3. The point clouds are analysed for Z Coordinate projection to track both the changes in minimum and maximum distance of the points and to verify that the background surface of the panels is aligned and flat with the global directions.
4. Point clouds' RGB values are converted to the CIELAB colour space with its three channels: L (Light), A (Green-Red), B (Yellow-Blue). The A channel is separated to remove the green screen in the following steps.
5. The A channel of the point cloud is converted to greyscale.
6. The greyscale colours of the points are converted to black and white based on the predefined threshold.
7. The white coloured points in the point cloud include all the objects other than the green screen and can be used as a mask to remove the background.
8. The point clouds are clustered using DBSCAN (Density-Based Spatial Clustering of Applications with Noise) algorithm and then a minimum oriented bounding box is calculated for each cluster.
9. All the point clouds with less than half the volume of the biggest bounding box are removed to isolate the 3D printed panel and in the end all the isolated objects are aligned using the ICP (Iterative Closest Point) algorithm for fine alignment of all the panels with the first stabilized 3D scan.

Our pipeline (Fig. 6) is developed in python and can run in batch mode. The processing of 72 scans of a raw volume of one GB takes five minutes.

Fig. 6. Analysis of the deformation of a small panel over time and correlation to weather data. We compare the incremental geometric change.

The analysis of the data can take place in an overall or incremental mode (Fig. 6). While the former shows, where and how much changes happen, the latter provides an understanding when the changes happen. Using the weather data graph, we can illustrate the environmental reasons for change.

Fig. 7. Overlay of 23 scans taken in the evening from 73 scans of capture session 2 after data processing and analysis of the total movement of each point. The juxtaposition of incremental analysis (top row) and the weather graph, indicates periods of change and reveals that after initial changes in the outdoor environment, rain is the main factor for change in the panel. A comparison of each step to the initial state (bottom row) shows that parts in the lower section of the panel move initially quite far out (10.9 mm) but retract later.

5.3 Focused behaviour analysis – region based

Information provided in the scans, such as on material color and relative depth can be used to isolate regions of interest in the 3D scan data of the objects. The information can stem from the original data capture or be a result of a subsequent analysis, which appends the resulting information of e.g. their relative-position, their cantilever etc. onto each voxel.

In our pipeline we encode this information as the voxel colour, which provide a straightforward mean to cluster voxels into different regions. This region and their behaviour can then be analysed in isolation.

While color captured from RGB cameras seems to be an efficient way to detect materials, we find that the colour appearance is impacted by sunlight and outdoor conditions such as snow. We try to mitigate this effect by weather condition based scheduling or the use of night data capture with artificial light from the camera, but that in the former the consistency is lacking and that artificial light needs to be setup really well in order to achieve a good lighting and that this photo studio like lighting is difficult to achieve in outdoor conditions.

Fig. 8. Isolation of similar regions in a 3D scan based on captured color (left) or data generated in post processing (right).

5.4 Focused analysis of the behaviour of features

The analysis of deviations between point clouds on a global or region based level provides good insight into general material behavior. However, the quantification of the differences in e.g. histograms (Fig. 4) is hard to interpret, and it is challenging to identify how much each area moved.

A voxel-based analysis (Fig. provides means to reduce the ambiguity inherent to any analysis of point cloud-based data to quantify the movement of specific areas over time e.g., edge features. For this we transform instances of the captured point clouds into models with Voxels of equal size. Voxels are created in spatial units, that include points within the point clouds bounding box.

For the analysis we assume a material with a relatively linear and homogeneous behaviour, as our bio-polymer, and can assume that the relative position of a feature in the panel does not change too much between time increments of the scans. We track the relative position of a voxel in different 3D scans, by creating minimum bounding boxes for each scan and divide this into a desired number of sections. This adaptive sections are used to find intersections with the grid of voxels in each scan. In this way, it is possible to trace features, such as voxels on the edges, over time, and quantify the amount and vector of movement per time step and overall.

The first application of this approach took place on the few datasets we gathered in data capture session 1 (Fig.9). The method allowed us to vectors quantify the changes and path of movement between each capture, despite the panel's heavy deformation time. Subsequently we applied the method on the data from the second capture with a larger bio-polymer panel (Fig. 10).

Here we find that we need to change the way, how we voxelise the point cloud data. In case of the data from the first data capture session point clouds were converted to meshes to produce voxels (Fig. 9). In our second version pipeline voxels are produced directly from point cloud. This produces better definition in the resulting ge-

ometry, as features such as holes can be maintained in the conversion and reduces processing time.

Fig. 9. First prototype of a voxel-based feature analysis applied on Panel 4 of the first data capture session. The tracking results show that on average the left side of the panel warped between 27.26mm to 42.63mm while on the other side it is equal to 29.00mm to 42.05mm. Tracking voxels in the middle of the model reveals that the minimum deformation happened in this area with the amount of 16mm to 19mm.

Fig. 100. Transformation of 3D scan into voxel format and analysis of timesteps (from left to right): initial point cloud, derived voxel model in high resolution with colours, Height Analysis, tracing and quantification of key areas across several 3d scans.

The analysis of the data from capture session 1 shows, that the small panel movement changes over the course time. It first elongated in response to the outdoor environment and then showed warp in parts of the panel where it is less thick up to 10mm and after that protrusion up to 15mm in the thick part of the panel.

In the second capture session, the feature-based change detection reveals that the changes mostly occur on the bottom part of the panel ranging from 11mm to 14.59mm on the right and 9.97mm to 18.57mm on the left side of the panel. Tracking the changes in the middle shows a range of 9.97mm to 18.44mm with no change in

the top part of the panel. All of these suggest elongation as the changes mainly occur on the bottom part of the panel and a combination of the three changes such as protrusion and warp due increase in red box volume by 203%.

The well-structured voxel representation of the objects provides a base for further statistical exploration and quantification of change over the course of time, as e.g. layers or regions within the voxel object can be analysed separately.

6 Conclusion

Adding the third dimension in the observation of outdoor structures provides means to gain novel insights into an object's behavior over time that allows for reasoning and understanding that goes beyond current state of art.

The developed methods allow the capturing of 3D information of changes in objects over long period of time in outdoor environments. The developed sensor framework is robust, runs autonomously and provides in its second iteration a resilient way to capture and transfer data to a safe repository in the cloud. We developed hardware and capturing protocols, which allows to capture data, which is of homogenous quality and to a big degree independent of the challenging effects of weather phenomena.

We developed a versatile pipeline for large time-based 3d scan data sets, which can be automatically stabilized, aligned, converted into voxel representation. We find that especially this format is well suited to analyze and quantify e.g. deviations of critical geometric features between each increment. Our method provides novel means to correlate and quantify the effect of different outdoor climates on the behavior of objects and deduct information for the further development of biopolymer recipes, printing strategies and coatings.

In our project we abandoned a general one solution fits all approach and demonstrate instead, that with a few components highly project specific data pipelines can be created. The combination and hybridization of captured information provides a good mean to extract information regarding project and site specific questions.

While our system is a prototype and the resolution and achievable depth of the used camera system is limited, we can track the movement of a series of elements and establish new quantified insights. This have been crucial for the further material and design development of our biopolymer panels. A transfer of the technique into other areas of application is already possible. An application on larger scale structure will be possible with an advance in depth camera technology.

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